

PUBLIC AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION TOWARDS ADR REPORTING

***Dr. Saritha M., Ms Asfara TMV, Ms. Fathimath Shifana, Ms Jazeela NT and Mr. Jasim KV**

Professor, Crescent College of Pharmaceutical Sciences.

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*Corresponding Author

Dr. Saritha M.

Professor, Crescent College of
Pharmaceutical Sciences.

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INTRODUCTION

ADVERSE DRUG REACTION

Pharmacovigilance is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as 'the science and activities relating to the detection, assessment, understanding and prevention of adverse effects or any other drug-related problem'. It plays a vital role in ensuring that doctors, together with the patient, have enough information to make a decision when it comes to choosing a drug for treatment.^[1]

The main objectives of pharmacovigilance involve exhibiting the efficacy of drugs by monitoring their adverse effect profile for many years from the lab to the pharmacy; tracking any drastic effects of drugs improving public health and safety in relation to the use of medicines; encouraging the safe, rational and cost-effective use of drugs; promoting understanding,

education and clinical training in pharmacovigilance; and effective communication to the generic public.^[2]

In addition, providing information to consumers, practitioners and regulators on the effective use of drugs along with designing programs and procedures for collecting and analyzing reports from patients and clinicians conclude the objectives of pharmacovigilance studies.^[2]

As per WHO, ADR is defined as Any response to a drug which is noxious and unintended, and which occurs at doses normally used in man for prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy of disease, or for the modification of physiological function".^[3] Classification Of Adverse drug

reactions include:

Type-A (Augmented): Commonest (up to 70%)-Dose dependent, severity increases with dose.

Type-B (Bizarre): Rare, idiosyncratic, genetically determined, unpredictable, mechanisms are unknown, Serious, can be fatal; unrelated to the dose.

Type-C (Continuous drug use): Occurs as a result of continuous drug use. May be irreversible, unexpected, unpredictable.

Type-D (Delayed): Delayed occurrence of ADRs, even after the cessation of treatment.

Type-E (End of dose): Withdrawal reactions Occurs typically with the depressant drugs.

Type-F (Failure of therapy): Results from the ineffective treatment.^[3]

Detection of Unknown Adverse Reactions

ADR reporting allows for the identification of previously unknown or rare adverse reactions associated with medications. Early detection of such reactions can lead to prompt intervention, preventing further harm to patients.^[4] ADR monitoring for safety evaluation is a complex process. Some of the generally followed monitoring methods are case reports, cohort studies, Record linkage system, patient questionnaires, intensive monitoring.^[3]

ARD Reporting Sources for Pharmacovigilance

The activity that is most essentially associated with pharmacovigilance is adverse event reporting. ADR reporting involves the receipt, triage, data entering, assessment, distribution, reporting and archiving of data and documentation.^[5] The source of ADR reports include spontaneous reports from healthcare professionals (doctors, nurses, pharmacist, paramedics), solicited reports from patient support programs, pharmaceutical clinical or post marketing studies by pharmaceuticals, literature sources of academic research and reports of drug regulatory authorities themselves. For pharmaceutical companies ADR reporting is a regulatory requirement in India for 4 years after marketing a new drug entity.^[5] Spontaneous (yellow card) reporting of ADRs remains the most widely used and cost effective surveillance system and is the cornerstone of safety monitoring of drugs in clinical practice. It detects previously unrecognized adverse reactions and identifies risk factors that predispose to drug toxicity and investigates causality. In addition to identifying drug safety problems, it

helps to facilitate risk-benefit judgments and comparisons within therapeutic Categories.^[6] In the early years of pharmacovigilance, reporting ADRs was restricted to healthcare professionals (HCPs), HCPs and patients can now report suspected ADRs to spontaneous reporting systems. In 2012, there was a major change at the European Commission level, with the publication of pharmacovigilance legislation: Directive 2010/84/EU and Regulation No 1235/2010. One of the major changes comprised the empowerment and emphasis given to citizens as an additional source of information, enabling them to directly report suspected ADRs.^[7]

It is acknowledged that the type of information reported by patients and HCPs are different. Patients' reports provide new information, including more subjective and detailed symptom descriptions of how ADRs impact daily life. HCPs report more objective and clinically related information. The information provided by both populations demonstrates a positive contribution to obtain a more complete and full knowledge of reported ADRs.^[7] Common barriers to patient reporting of ADRs included poor awareness about available reporting systems, uncertainty about who should be responsible for submitting the ADR reports, and lack of feedback for submitted reports. Barriers that were unique to patient reporting were mailing costs, prior negative experiences and resolved ADRs.^[8] Strategies to enhance patient ADR reporting should focus on the most common and feasible barriers to address. If patients are unaware of available reporting systems, how they work and how they are accessed, their contributions will continue to decline. First, strategies are needed to increase patients' awareness of reporting systems, and HCPs' awareness that patients can report on their own.^[8] Reporting should be made easy and convenient by Email/website, telephone, fax etc. This can improve the quantum and quality of the reports.^[6]

OTC MEDICATION

Over-the-counter (OTC) medicines are therapeutic products that pharmacies or retail outlets sell directly to consumers, unlike prescription medicines, which can only be dispensed based on a physician's valid prescription.^[9] OTC medications contribute to prevention and therapy for a broad spectrum of minor conditions, including but not limited to headaches, the common cold, musculoskeletal pain, allergies, and heartburn.^[9]

Usually, a regulatory agency chooses OTC medicines based on their safety and effectiveness profiles.^[9] There are several important aspects of consumer practice of medication, including

non-adherence, sharing of drugs, and self-medication. Self-medication involves a person purchasing medications to treat their symptoms without consulting a healthcare professional.^[9]

According to World Health Organization (WHO) drug information, self-medication is broadly accepted as an essential activity in healthcare with constant improvement in consumers' general knowledge, education, and socioeconomic status.^[9] Self-medication is self-care in which a person can recognize their symptoms immediately and can usually treat these symptoms with medications that are easily accessible, such as OTC medicines.^[9] The use of OTC drugs is associated with many advantages, including decreased doctor visits and lower costs compared with prescription drugs.^[10] Globally, inappropriate self-medication with OTC medicines has increased and is recognized as a public concern. Misuse of various painkillers, vitamins, and sedatives have been reported among university students, and OTC drug misuse has become more popular among young adults.^[9]

Potentially inappropriate medication use from self-medication may occur due to a lack of knowledge. This may include use for a wrong indication and administration of incorrect dosages. Poor knowledge and incorrect use of OTC medicine will lead to health risks such as adverse side effects, drug interactions and overdose. Several studies have shown that lack of knowledge of OTC medicine use and poor attitudes toward proper medicine handling and safe use.^[9]

However, the misuse of OTC drugs can result in adverse reactions, drug interactions, overdosing, and other medication-related issues. Therefore, the public should be trained in the safe use of OTC drugs to increase their knowledge and understanding of potential dangers and promote responsible self-care.^[10] Therefore more awareness of patients and pharmacists about OTC drugs is required to prevent the harmful effects. Thus, this study aimed to improve the public awareness and perception towards the ADR reporting and OTC medication as it plays a pivotal role in ensuring medication safety and promoting responsible healthcare practices.

METHODOLOGY

AIM

The aim of our study is to assess the public awareness and perception towards ADR reporting and OTC medication.

1. Primary objective

To enhance public awareness and perceptions towards ADR reporting and by fostering understanding, we aim to empower individuals to recognize the importance of ADR reporting.

2. Secondary objectives

To assess and enhance the understanding, awareness, and safe usage practices of over-the-counter medications among the general public.

STUDY SETTING

A three-month study was conducted among the public across diverse backgrounds. Utilising Google Forms, the survey targeted a wide range of participants to assess knowledge and attitudes towards medication safety.

STUDY DESIGN

A cross-sectional descriptive survey was conducted over three months, targeting diverse age groups to gauge public awareness and perception regarding ADR reporting and OTC medications. Google Forms were employed for questionnaire distribution, ensuring accessibility.

This method was chosen for its flexibility and scalability, enabling the inclusion of a wide range of participants across various age groups. By utilizing Google Forms, we ensured ease of distribution and data collection, promoting higher response rates and allowing for anonymous participation. This approach facilitates a comprehensive analysis of public awareness and perception towards ADR reporting and OTC medications, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of pharmacovigilance efforts.

STUDY DEVELOPMENT

A questionnaire approach was used in this study. Online questionnaires were developed by using the style and format of some of the questions used in previous research works and were created using google forms. Since the journals we reviewed developed questionnaires for the public. The study questionnaire included specific questions to assess the public awareness and perception towards ADR reporting and OTC medication.

CONDUCTS OF STUDY QUESTIONNAIRE

The study questionnaire consisted of 27 questions. It comprised 3 sections. Section one had three questions that explored the demographic information of respondents like, age, gender and their educational level.

The section two consisted of 14 questions to assess the public awareness and perception towards ADR reporting. The first two questions are to identify the public knowledge about pharmacovigilance and the remaining 12 questions are regarding the people's knowledge about ADR and their attitude and perceptions towards ADR reporting.

The section three consists of 10 questions which helps to assess the public's knowledge perception and awareness towards the usage of OTC medications.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

Individuals aged 18 and above included.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

Non cooperative public and children.

QUESTIONNAIRE DISTRIBUTION AND DATA COLLECTION

Questionnaire was prepared using google forms and shared through email and Whatsapp messenger. Prior to the participation in the study, the objectives and the purpose of the study were explained to the public through message. Participant's personal information was collected by the self-administered questionnaire. The study was conducted online using form-based questionnaires for the convenience of the public as it would be difficult for them to find time for the interview between their busy schedules. The questions were created in the English language because this is the medium of education in the country. It took only 5-10 minutes to fill the questionnaire. The questionnaire was distributed among the public living in diverse backgrounds through WhatsApp and email with the help of friends, seniors, teachers and various other helping hands. With the support we could reach the target (n=150) within a short period of time.

RESULTS

DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

A total of 140 responses were obtained throughout this study. The survey revealed a significant gender imbalance, with female respondents representing the majority at 73.6%,

while male respondents accounted for 26.4%. Furthermore, the age distribution skewed heavily towards younger demographics, with 91.4% falling within the 18-36 age bracket, indicating a higher level of engagement among younger individuals in discussions regarding adverse drug reaction reporting and over-the-counter medication usage. In terms of educational attainment, the majority of respondents held bachelor's degrees (78.6%), followed by master's degrees (11.4%), and a smaller percentage with doctorates (10%).

Table 1: Demographic data.

CATEGORIES	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
GENDER		
Female	103	73.6%
Male	37	26.4%
AGE		
18 - 36	128	91.4%
37 - 55	12	8.6%
56 or older	NIL	NIL
EDUCATIONAL LEVEL		
Bachelors degree	110	78.6%
Masters degree	16	11.4%
Doctorates or others	14	10%

GRAPH 1: GENDER.

GRAPH 3: EDUCATION LEVEL.

PUBLIC AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION TOWARDS ADR REPORTING

The survey on public awareness and perception towards adverse drug reaction (ADR) reporting involved 140 participants.

Awareness of Pharmacovigilance and PVPI

Most respondents (81.4%) are familiar with the term pharmacovigilance, and 65% know about the Pharmacovigilance Programme of India (PVPI). A high percentage (90%) understand what an adverse drug reaction is, with the majority perceiving ADRs as very harmful (40%) or somewhat serious (46.4%).

GRAPH 4: AWARENESS OF PHARMACOVIGILANCE AND PVPI.

UNDERSTANDING OF ADRS

A high percentage (90%) understand what an adverse drug reaction is, with the majority perceiving ADRs as very harmful (40%) or somewhat serious (46.4%), while 1.4% do not see them as harmful, and 12.1% are unsure.

GRAPH 5: UNDERSTANDING OF ADRs.

Willingness to report ADRs

When it comes to reporting non-serious ADRs, 59.3% of participants indicated they would report them, showing a willingness to engage in ADR reporting. An overwhelming 94.3% believe it is important to educate patients about ADRs and the reporting process, highlighting the perceived need for increased awareness.

GRAPH 6: WILLINGNESS TO REPORT ADR.

Sources of ADR information and Encouragement to report ADRs

Participants primarily seek ADR information from pharmacists (64.3%) and physicians (50.7%), indicating trust in healthcare professionals. However, a little more than half (55%) reported that their healthcare providers advise them to report ADRs.

GRAPH 7: SOURCE OF ADR INFORMATION.

Preferred methods for reporting ADR and Notification of serious ADRs

Regarding preferred methods for reporting ADRs, most respondents (67.9%) prefer reporting directly to health workers, with smaller percentages opting for manual forms (15.7%) or smartphone applications (16.4%). For serious ADRs, 32.1% think physicians should be

notified, followed by pharmacovigilance centers (24.3%) and pharmacists (20%).

GRAPH 8: PREFERRED METHOD TO REPORT ADR.

GRAPH 9: NOTIFICATION ABOUT SERIOUS ADR.

Motivating consumers to report ADRs and Barriers to ADR reporting

To improve ADR reporting, 45.7% of respondents suggest increasing awareness about the ADR reporting system. Challenges to reporting include a lack of knowledge about the importance of ADR reporting, pharmacovigilance centre, the reporting process, and uncertainty about whether symptoms are related to medication.

GRAPH 10: MOTIVATION TO REPORT ADR.

GRAPH 11: BARRIERS OF ADR REPORTING.

Table 2: Assessment of public awareness and perception towards ADR reporting.

SI. NO	QUESTIONS	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	Have you heard about the term pharmacovigilance?	114	81.4%
	Yes	26	18.6%
2.	Have you heard about the PVPI (Pharmacovigilance programme of India)?		65%
	Yes	91	35%
3.	Do you know what is "Adverse drug reaction" mean?	126	90%
	Yes	14	10%

	Do you think that ADR is harmful?		
	Very harmful	56	40%
	Somewhat serious	65	46.4%
	Not harmful	2	1.4%
	I don't know	17	12.1%
5.	If you were suffered from a non-serious ADR, would you report that?		
	Yes	83	59.3%
	No	57	40.7%
6.	Is it important to educate patients about ADR and how to report one?		
	Yes	132	94.3%
	No	8	5.7%
7.	Do you ask about your medication's ADR?		
	Yes	96	68.6%
	No	44	31.4%
8.	Which of the following resources do you use to search about an ADR?		
	Physician	71	50.7%
	Pharmacist	90	64.3%
	Pharmacovigilance centre	25	17.9%
	Consumers	5	3.6%
	Others	35	25%
9.	Does your physician or pharmacist ask you to report any ADR that may happen to you?		
	Yes	77	55%
	No	63	45%
10.	Which of the following ways do you prefer to report ADR?	95	67.9%
	Report to health workers	22	15.7%
	Fill a specific form and send it manually	23	16.4%
	Using specific application on smart phone		
11.	Who should be notified about any serious ADR?	45	32.1%
	Physician	28	20%
	Pharmacist	2	1.4%
	Nurses	34	24.3%
	Pharmacovigilance centre	3	2.1%
	World Health Organization	21	15%
	Medical team		
	Consumers	7	5%
12.	Which agency should evaluate the ADR reports?	114	81.4%

	• Pharmacovigilance centre	14	10%
	• World Health Organisation Ministry of health	12	8.6%
	How to motivate consumers to report any ADR?	32	22.9%
		64	45.7%
13.	Make the reporting processes easier	12	8.6%
	Increase the awareness about ADR reporting system		
	Make it mandatory for patients	32	22.9%
	Provide a 7/24 phone numbers to receive patients call		
	Why patients do not report ADR?	35	25%
	Does not know if it is from the medication or not	4	2.9%
	The ADR is not serious	5	3.6%
14.	Common ADR		
	Doesn't know about the Pharmacovigilance centre	15	10.7%
	Doesn't know about the importance of ADR reporting	56	40%
	Doesn't know how to report	25	17.9%

PUBLIC AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION TOWARDS OTC MEDICATION

The survey on public awareness and perception towards OTC medication involved 140 participants, aiming to understand their frequency of OTC drug usage, sources of information, familiarity with various OTC medications, and attitudes towards the safety, regulation, and education of these drugs.

Frequency of OTC drug usage and Source of information

The results revealed that the majority of respondents (67.1%) use OTC medications rarely or never, indicating a low frequency of usage. Most participants (65%) rely on healthcare professionals for information about OTC drugs, showing a high level of trust in professional advice.

GRAPH 12: FREQUENCY OF OTC DRUG USAGE.

GRAPH 13: SOURCE OF INFORMATION ABOUT OTC DRUG.

Familiarity with OTC drugs and Information and Education from health care providers

Pain relievers were the most familiar category, known by 55.5% of respondents. Nearly half (49.3%) of the participants reported receiving information or education about OTC medications from healthcare providers, suggesting that there is room for improvement in patient education.

GRAPH 14: FAMILIARITY WITH OTC DRUGS.

GRAPH 15: INFORMATION AND EDUCATION ABOUT OTC FROM HCP.

Identifying unsuitable OTC medications for certain populations and understanding difference between Generic and Brand name

Only 35% could confidently identify OTC medications that are unsuitable for certain populations, such as children or pregnant women, indicating a significant gap in specific knowledge. A significant portion (43.6%) understands the difference between generic and brand name OTC medications, while 29.3% do not.

GRAPH 16: IDENTIFYING UNSUITABLE OTC DRUGS FOR CERTAIN POPULATIONS.

GRAPH 17: UNDERSTANDING DIFFERENCE BETWEEN BRAND NAME AND GENERIC NAME.

Safety perceptions of OTC medications

When it comes to safety perceptions, a majority (54.3%) do not believe that OTC medications are safe for self-use without consulting healthcare professionals, reflecting a cautious attitude towards self-medication.

GRAPH 18: SAFETY PERCEPTIONS OF OTC MEDICATIONS.

Regulation of OTC medications and education on its proper usage

Furthermore, 71.4% of participants support stricter regulation of OTC medications to ensure safety and efficacy, highlighting concerns about their current regulatory status. An overwhelming 85.7% believe that consumers should receive more education about the proper use of OTC medications, underscoring the perceived necessity for better public awareness.

GRAPH 19: EDUCATION ON PROPER USAGE OF OTC MEDICATIONS.

GRAPH 20: REGULATION OF OTC MEDICATIONS.

Table 3: Assessment of public awareness and perception towards OTC medications.

	QUESTIONS	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE
1.	How often do you use OTC drugs?		
	Daily	6	4.3%
	Weekly	12	8.6%
	Monthly	28	20%
	Rarely/Never	94	67.1%
2.	What is your primary source of information about OTC drugs?		
	Health care professionals	91	65%
	Family and friends	20	14.3%
	Online sources	26	18.6%
	Others	3	2.1%
3.	Which OTC drugs are you most familiar with?		
	Pain relievers	78	55.53%
	Allergy medication	34	24.13%
	Cough and cold medicine	18	12.63%
	Others	10	7.63%
4.	Have you ever received information or education about OTC medications from a healthcare provider		

	Yes	69	49.3%
	No	43	30.7%
	Not sure	28	20%
5.	Can you identify any OTC medication that are not suitable for use in certain population(eg:- children, pregnant women)?		
	Yes	49	35%
	No	35	25%
	Partially	56	40%
6.	Do you know the difference between generic and brand name of the OTC medication?		
	Yes	61	43.6%
	No	41	29.3%
	Partially	38	27.1%
7.	Do you believe that OTC medications are generally safe for self-		
	use without consulting a		
	health care		
	professionals?		
	Yes	28	20%
	No	76	54.3%
	Unsure	36	25.7%
8.	Do you believe that OTC medications should be more strictly regulated to ensure safety and efficacy?		
	Yes	100	71.4%
	No	24	17.1%
	Unsure	16	11.4%
9.	Do you believe that consumers should receive more education and information about the proper use of OTC medications?		
	Yes	120	85.7%
	No	13	9.3%
	Unsure	7	5%

DISCUSSION

The study highlights several key insights into public awareness and perceptions regarding ADR reporting, and the use of OTC medications. It is evident that while there is a significant awareness of pharmacovigilance and the Pharmacovigilance Programme of India (PVPI), understanding and proactive behaviour regarding ADR reporting are not uniformly practiced among the public.

A substantial number of respondents are aware of the term pharmacovigilance and its importance, yet there are gaps in understanding the specific actions required to report ADRs. Many individuals know what an ADR is and recognize its potential harm, but there remains a hesitancy to report non-serious ADRs. This reluctance can be attributed to a lack of knowledge on how to report ADRs, the perceived complexity of the reporting process, and uncertainty about the significance of reporting minor reactions.

One of the prominent findings is that most respondents acknowledge the importance of educating patients about ADRs and how to report them. This indicates a general willingness to engage with pharmacovigilance activities if provided with adequate information and support. Healthcare providers, including physicians and pharmacists, play a crucial role in this education. However, the data suggests that not all healthcare professionals consistently ask patients to report ADRs, indicating a need for more proactive communication strategies in clinical settings.

The study also sheds light on the sources of information that patients rely on for ADR-related queries. Pharmacists are frequently consulted, which underscores the necessity for pharmacists to be well-equipped with up-to-date knowledge and resources to advise patients accurately. Additionally, the preference for using digital tools such as smartphone applications for ADR reporting suggests an opportunity to leverage technology to simplify and encourage reporting processes. In order to motivate patients for reporting ADRs Implement incentives for patients who report ADRs, such as recognition or small rewards highlight success stories where ADR reporting led to significant improvements in drug safety, create community programs or workshops focused on the impact of pharmacovigilance to motivate public participation.

Regarding OTC medications, the survey reveals cautious use, with most respondents using them rarely or never. There is a considerable reliance on healthcare professionals for

information.

However, the findings indicate that the public's understanding of the differences between generic and brand-name medications and the suitability of OTC drugs for specific populations (e.g., children, pregnant women) is limited. So that Develop clear, easy-to-understand guidelines about OTC medication use for vulnerable populations (e.g., children, pregnant women) and distribute them widely.

Ensure that these guidelines are available in multiple languages and formats to cater to diverse populations.

Regularly update and review OTC medication guidelines based on the latest research and pharmacovigilance data.

There is also a significant belief that OTC medications should be more strictly regulated, reflecting public concern about safety and efficacy.

Challenges in providing comprehensive patient counseling by pharmacists were identified, primarily due to time constraints and the high workload. To address this, strategies such as integrating pharmacists more effectively into healthcare teams, providing continuous professional training, and optimizing pharmacy workflows to allow more time for patient interaction are essential.

In conclusion, while there is a foundational awareness of pharmacovigilance and ADRs among the public, there are significant areas for improvement in education, communication, and reporting practices. Addressing these issues through comprehensive strategies involving healthcare professionals, regulatory bodies, and technological advancements can enhance public participation in pharmacovigilance and lead to safer medication practices and improved health outcomes.

CONCLUSION

While there is considerable awareness of pharmacovigilance and the Pharmacovigilance Programme of India (PVPI), significant gaps in knowledge and behavior persist. Addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach.

Enhancing public awareness and understanding of pharmacovigilance is crucial. Despite high

levels of awareness, a notable portion of the population remains uninformed. Public education campaigns using social media, television, and print media, along with collaborations with healthcare providers, can effectively disseminate information. Educational programs in schools and community centers and user-friendly materials such as brochures and online resources can further explain the importance of ADR reporting.

Simplifying the ADR reporting process is essential. Many respondents find the process inconvenient or are unaware of how to report ADRs. Developing user-friendly digital tools like mobile apps and online platforms can make reporting more accessible. Providing 24/7 support through hotlines can assist individuals needing help. Targeted campaigns emphasizing the significance of reporting all ADRs and regular training for healthcare providers to encourage and assist patients in reporting ADRs are also crucial.

Improving trust and communication between patients and healthcare providers is foundational. Healthcare providers should proactively discuss potential ADRs and the importance of reporting them. Regular training on effective communication strategies can foster open dialogues, making patients feel more comfortable discussing medication-related concerns.

Enhancing the safety and proper use of OTC medications is also necessary. Stricter regulation, better labeling, and comprehensive educational initiatives are needed. Public education initiatives and healthcare provider guidance during consultations can inform consumers about proper OTC medication use and potential risks.

In conclusion, addressing gaps in public awareness and behavior regarding ADR reporting and OTC medication use requires a comprehensive strategy. Public education campaigns, healthcare provider training, simplified reporting systems, stricter regulatory measures, and enhanced communication can collectively enhance public participation in pharmacovigilance, leading to safer medication practices and improved public health outcomes.

1. s of those with limited technological access

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APPENDIX**PUBLIC AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION TOWARDS ADVERSE DRUG REACTION REPORTING AND OTC MEDICATIONS**

Crescent College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Madayipara, Payangadi, Kannur
Pharmacovigilance project

DATA COLLECTION QUESTIONNAIRE

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA
Name:.....
Gender:.....
Age:.....
Qualification:.....

QUESTIONS**PUBLIC AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION TOWARDS ADR REPORTING**

1. Have you heard about the term Pharmacovigilance?
 - Yes
 - No
2. Have you heard about the PVPI (pharmacovigilance programme of India)?
 - Yes
 - No
3. Do you know what is "Adverse drug reaction" mean?
 - Yes
 - No
4. Do you think that ADR is harmful?
 - Very harmful
 - Somewhat serious
 - I don't know
5. If you were suffered from a non-serious ADR, would you report that?
 - Yes
 - No

6. Is it important to educate patients about ADR and how to report one?
 - Yes
 - No
7. Do you ask about your medication's ADR?
 - Yes
 - No
8. Which of the following resources do you use to search about an ADR?
 - Physician
 - Pharmacist
 - Pharmacovigilance centre
9. Does your physician or pharmacist ask you to report any ADR that may happen to you?
 - Yes
 - No
10. Which of the following ways do you prefer to report ADRs?
 - Report to health workers
 - Fill a specific form and sent it manually
 - Using specific application on smartphone
11. Who should be notified about any serious ADR?
 - Physician
 - Pharmacist
 - Nurses
 - Pharmacovigilance centres
 - World health organization
 - Medical team
 - Consumers
12. What agency should evaluate the ADRs reports?
 - Pharmacovigilance centre
 - World health organization
 - Ministry of health
13. How to motivate the consumers to report any ADR?
 - Make the reporting process easier
 - Increase the awareness about ADR reporting system
 - Make it mandatory for patients
 - Provide a 7/24 phone number to receive patients calls to report any ADR

14. Why patients do not report ADRs?

- Does not know if it is from the medication or not
- The ADR is not serious
- Common ADR
- Doesn't know about the pharmacovigilance centre
- Doesn't know about the importance of ADR REPORTING
- Doesn't know how to report

PUBLIC AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION TOWARDS OTC MEDICATION

15. How often do you use over-the-counter drugs?

- Daily
- Weekly
- Monthly
- Rarely/Never

16. What is your primary source of information about over-the-counter drugs?

- Health care professionals (doctor, pharmacist)
- Family and friends
- Online sources (websites, forums)
- Other (please specify)

17. Which over-the-counter drugs are you most familiar with?

- Pain relievers
- Allergy medication
- Cough and cold
- Others

18. Have you ever received information or education about over-the-counter medications from a healthcare provider?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

19. Can you identify any over-the-counter medications that are not suitable for use in certain populations (e.g., children, pregnant women)?

- Yes
- No
- Partially

20. Do you know the difference between generic and brand-name over the counter medication?

- Yes
- No
- Partially

21. Do you believe that over-the-counter medications are generally safe for self-use without consulting a healthcare professional?

- Yes
- No
- Unsure

22. Do you believe that over-the-counter medications should be more strictly regulated to ensure safety and efficacy?

- Yes
- No
- Unsure

23. Do you believe that consumers should receive more education or information about the proper use of over-the-counter medications?

- Yes
- No
- Unsure